

Edition 0

A Pyomo Approach to Deal with Graph Related
Optimization Problems

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A Pyomo Approach to Deal with Graph Related Optimization Problems

What is the shortest path between two given nodes?

How to answer the following questions?

- What are all shortest independent paths between two given nodes?
- What are the all paths between two given nodes?

How complex are these problems?

Here is a sample Graph, Let's assume the starting and Ending nodes are 1 and 20, respectively.

Image by author

Q1: What is the shortest path between two given nodes?

The answer of this problem is super easy. A linear programming formulation can do the job as follows:

Shortest Path

$$OF = \sum_{ij} W_{ij} f_{ij}$$

$$G_i \times ST_i - D_i = \sum_j f_{ij} - f_{ji} \quad \forall i$$

$$0 \leq f_{ij} \leq 1 \quad \forall ij \in Edges$$

$$0 \leq G_i \leq 1 \quad \text{Real variable}$$

In this formulation :

W_{ij} is the weight of edge connecting node i and node j (parameter)

G_i is a real variable representing the source on node i

D_i is a binary parameter representing the existence of demand (sink) on node i . If it is 0 then there is no demand on node i

ST_i is a binary parameter representing the demand (sink) on node i . If it is 0 then there is no demand on node i

Properties:

The model is LP and is scalable for large graphs (with several nodes and edges.)

It finds the shortest path in one run (there might be more than one solution with the same total length of path)

The **Pyomo** code for solving the shortest Path problem is as follows:

```
model = AbstractModel()
model.i = RangeSet(N)
model.j = Set(initialize=model.i)
model.flow = Var(model.i,model.j, initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.G = Var(initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.start = Param(model.i, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
model.demand = Param(model.i, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)

def rule_C1(model,i):
    return model.G*model.start[i]- model.demand[i] == sum(model.flow[ii,j]- model.flow[j,ii]
        for (ii,j) in allowed if i==ii )
model.C1 = Constraint(model.i,rule=rule_C1)

def rule_OF(model):
    return sum(model.flow[i,j]*allowed[i,j] for (i,j) in allowed)
model.obj1 = Objective(rule=rule_OF, sense=minimize)
```

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Here is the simulation result:

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There are 8 nodes in this shortest path [1,3,12,11,10,16,17,19,20]

Q2: What are the all shortest independent paths between two given nodes?

Here is the problem formulation:

All Independent Shortest Paths

$$OF = \sum_{i,j} D_{i,j} f_{i,j}$$
$$G_i \times ST_i - D_i = \sum_j f_{i,j} - f_{j,i} \quad \forall i$$
$$0 \leq f_{i,j} \leq inc_i \times inc_j \quad \forall ij \in Edges \quad inc_i = 0/1$$

Parameter = 1 if node i already considered, 0 not used yet

$ST_i = 0$ Parameter = 0 if i is not the starting point

$ST_i = 1$ Parameter = 1 if i is the starting point

This is the Pyomo code

```
model = AbstractModel()
model.i = RangeSet(N)
model.j = Set(initialize=model.i)
model.include = Param(model.i, initialize=dicini, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
model.flow = Var(model.i,model.j, initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.G = Var(initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.start = Param(model.i, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
model.demand = Param(model.i, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
def rule_C1(model,i):
    return model.G*model.start[i]- model.demand[i] ==
sum(model.include[i]*model.include[j]*model.flow[i,j])-
model.include[i]*model.include[j]*model.flow[j,i] for (i,j) in allowed if i==i )
model.C1 = Constraint(model.i,rule=rule_C1)

def rule_C2A(model,i,j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.flow[i,j]<= model.include[i]
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.C2A = Constraint(model.i, model.j,rule=rule_C2A)

def rule_C2B(model,i,j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.flow[i,j]<= model.include[j]
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.C2B = Constraint(model.i, model.j,rule=rule_C2B)

def rule_OF(model):
    return sum(model.flow[i,j]*allowed[i,j] for (i,j) in allowed)
model.obj1 = Objective(rule=rule_OF, sense=minimize)
```

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Here is the results:

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It is an iterative procedure,

Step 0 : Solve the problem for the shortest path and save the path if there is any

Step 1: Remove the nodes that belong to the previous shourtest path

Step 3: Go to step 0

This model is based on linear programming and can be easily applied to large scale graphs. Some examples are as follows:

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Q3: What are the all paths between two given nodes?

The concept is very similar to the shortest path. First the shortest path is found and then a CUT is added to the problem and resolved to find the next path. The Idea is to find a new path without repeating the previously found ones. This procedure is repeated until there is no more feasible solution.

```

DIC={
  for (i,j) in allowed:
    DIC[i,j]=value(instance.U[i,j])
  expr=0
  for (i,j) in DIC:
    if DIC[i,j]==1:
      expr+=1-instance.U[i,j]
    else:
      expr+=instance.U[i,j]
  instance.C4.add( expr >= 1 )}

```

Initial formulation:

$$OF = \sum_{i,j} W_{i,j} U_{i,j}$$

$$G_i \times ST_i - D_i = \sum_j U_{i,j} - U_{j,i} \quad \forall i$$

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By adding these cuts, the algorithm will try to find new solutions with min costs. However, if we just consider the following formulation it will not generate reasonable paths. Let's give an example: The following answer is a feasible one but you can see the obtained graph is a disconnected one.

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In order to avoid this situation, we need to add some more constraints to make sure the graph is connected (after adding the cuts).

(I found more than 2000 different paths). Some of them are visualized here

$$\begin{aligned}
 OF &= \sum_{ij} W_{i,j} U_{i,j} \\
 G_i \times ST_i - D_i &= \sum_j U_{i,j} - U_{j,i} \quad \forall i \\
 GS_i \times ST_i - select_i / N &= \sum_j f_{i,j} - f_{j,i} \quad \forall i \\
 0 &\leq f_{i,j} \leq U_{i,j} \quad \forall ij \in Edges \\
 U_{i,j} + U_{j,i} &\leq 1 \quad \forall ij \in Edges \\
 \sum_j U_{i,j} &\leq 1 \quad \forall i \in Nodes \\
 \sum_j U_{j,i} &\leq 1 \quad \forall i \in Nodes \\
 U_{i,j} &\leq S_i \quad \forall ij \in Edges \\
 U_{i,j} &\leq S_j \quad \forall ij \in Edges
 \end{aligned}$$

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S_i is a binary variable indicating if the node i is in the path.

Here is the Pyomo model:

```
model = AbstractModel()
model.I = RangeSet(N)
model.J = Set(initialize=model.I)
model.F = Var(model.I, model.J, initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.U = Var(model.I, model.J, initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=Binary)
model.select = Var(model.I, initialize=1, bounds=(0,1), within=Binary)

model.G = Var(initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)
model.Gnew = Var(initialize=0, bounds=(0,1), within=NonNegativeReals)

model.start = Param(model.I, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
model.demand = Param(model.I, initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)
model.eps = Param(initialize=0, within=NonNegativeReals, mutable=True)

def rule_C1(model, i):
    return model.G*model.start[i]- model.demand[i] == sum(model.U[i,j]- model.U[j,i] for (i,j) in
allowed if i==i )
model.C1 = Constraint(model.I, rule=rule_C1)

def rule_B1(model, i):
    return model.Gnew*model.start[i]- model.select[i]/N == sum(model.F[i,j]- model.F[j,i] for (i,j)
in allowed if i==i )
model.B1 = Constraint(model.I, rule=rule_B1)

def rule_B2(model, i, j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.F[i,j]<= model.U[i,j]
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.B2 = Constraint(model.I, model.J, rule=rule_B2)

def rule_B3A(model, i, j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.U[i,j]<= model.select[i]
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.B3A = Constraint(model.I, model.J, rule=rule_B3A)

def rule_B3B(model, i, j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.U[i,j]<= model.select[j]
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.B3B = Constraint(model.I, model.J, rule=rule_B3B)

def rule_C3A(model, i, j):
    if (i,j) in allowed:
        return model.U[i,j]+model.U[j,i]<= 1
    else:
        return Constraint.Skip
model.C3A = Constraint(model.I, model.J, rule=rule_C3A)

def rule_C2(model):
    return sum( model.U[i,j]*allowed[i,j] for (i,j) in allowed)>= model.eps
model.C2 = Constraint(rule=rule_C2)

def rule_C5A(model, i):
    return sum(model.U[i,j] for j in model.J if (i,j) in allowed)<= 1
model.C5A = Constraint(model.I, rule=rule_C5A)

def rule_C5B(model, i):
    return sum(model.U[j,i] for j in model.J if (j,i) in allowed)<= 1
model.C5B = Constraint(model.I, rule=rule_C5B)

model.C4 = ConstraintList()
def rule_OF(model):
    return sum( model.U[i,j]*allowed[i,j] for (i,j) in allowed)
model.obj1 = Objective(rule=rule_OF, sense=minimize)
```

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We can also control the length of the paths or the number of allowed nodes in the path:

Limited the number of nodes in the path to 8 nodes

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Conclusion

Shortest path can be easily found with the LP formulation.

All independent shortest paths can be found using LP formulation (iterative method), there are usually few number of them exist.

All paths between two given nodes can be found using MILP formulation (iterative method), there are usually a large number of them exist.